

Synthesis of some New Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3(1*H*)-ones

M B HOGALE (DESHMUKH)*, (Ms) S D SHIRKE and D R KHARADE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 9 July 1992, revised 23 December 1992, accepted 23 February 1993

Owing to the interesting biological activities¹ of condensed benzofurans, the attention has focussed on benzofuran ring system. Recently, the syntheses of some new benzofuropyrazoles and benzofuropyrimidines have been reported². Herein we report the synthesis of some new benzofuropyrazoles.

Results and Discussion

2-(2,4-Dimethylphenoxy)propionic acid was prepared by the reaction of 2,4-dimethylphenol with 2-chloropropionic acid in presence of alkali followed by its polyphosphoric acid cyclisation to yield 2,5,7-trimethylbenzofuran-3(1*H*)-one (**3**). The formation of **3** was evidenced by disappearance of acidic OH signal at δ 10.4 in its pmr spectrum and a broad band around $3\ 500\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in ir spectrum. Compound **3** was further converted into **4** by reacting with ethyl chloroformate in acetone using potassium carbonate as a base. The formation of **4** was established by appearance of ester C=O band at $1\ 760\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in ir spectrum and a triplet at δ 1.1 and quartet at δ 4.2 in pmr spectrum. Compound **3** on nucleophilic acylation with substituted hydrazides followed by intramolecular cyclisation in methanol yielded target molecule *N*¹-substituted benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3(1*H*)-ones. The formation of **5** was confirmed by the disappearance of ester C=O band and appearance of two amido C=O bands at $1\ 700$ and $1\ 665\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in its ir spectrum (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-437 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer

R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc. 2-(2,4-Dimethylphenoxy)propionic acid was prepared as per literature method³.

2,5,7-Trimethylbenzofuran-3(1H)-one (3). 2-(2,4-Dimethylphenoxy)propionic acid (**2**; 0.05 mol) was added to a stirred solution of orthophosphoric acid (10 ml) containing phosphorous pentoxide (8 g), and the reaction mixture was heated gently at $80\text{--}100^\circ$ for 2 h, then cooled and poured into ice-water (250 ml). The reaction mixture was then neutralised with sodium bicarbonate to give a gummy solid which was extracted in chloroform. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a solid which was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 66° ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1710, 1600 and $1\ 060\ \text{cm}^{-1}$; δ (CDCl_3), 1.65 (3H, d, J 2.5 Hz, C-CH₃), 2.35 (6H, s, $2\times\text{ArCH}_3$), 4.6 (1H, q, C-H) and 6.6-7.1 (2H, m, ArH).

2-Carbethoxy-2,5,7-trimethylbenzofuran-3(1H)-one (4): To a mixture of **3** (0.02 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (0.02 mol) in acetone (25 ml), potassium carbonate (2.5 g) was added and then refluxed for 20 h, cooled and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was poured into ice-water and extracted in chloroform. Removal of chloroform gave viscous liquid which was purified by column chromatography using silica gel-G (benzene : chloroform, 95 : 5 v/v), b.p. $216^\circ/100\ \text{mm}$; ν_{max} (KBr) 1750, 1700, 1600 and $1\ 060\ \text{cm}^{-1}$; δ (CDCl_3) 1.1 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, CH₃), 1.7 (3H, s, C-CH₃), 2.3 (6H, s, $2\times\text{ArCH}_3$), 4.2 (2H, q, J 8.5 Hz, OCH₂) and 6.6-7.1 (2H, m, ArH).

- | | |
|---|--|
| 5a; R = 2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ - | g; R = 4-Cl, 5-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₂ - |
| b; R = 3-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ - | h; R = 2-OH, 5-Cl.C ₆ H ₃ - |
| c; R = 4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ - | i; R = 3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ - |
| d; R = 2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ - | j; R = 2-Cl. C ₆ H ₄ - |
| e; R = 4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ - | k; R = C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ - |
| f; R = 4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ - | l; R = C ₆ H ₅ - |

Scheme 1

3,5,7-Trimethyl, 2-arylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyrazol-3(1H)-one (5a) : A mixture of **4** (0.001 mol) and *o*-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 5 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with ice-water (150 ml) and the solid formed was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 132° (Found : C, 69.19; H, 5.31; N, 7.60. C₂₁H₂₀O₄N₂ requires : C, 69.23, H, 5.49; N, 7.69%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1700, 1665, 1600 and 1060 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃), 1.65 (3H, s, C-CH), 2.35 (9H, s, 3×ArCH₃), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂) 6.6–7.3 (6H, m, ArH).

Other compounds (yields 54–79%) were prepared in a similar manner : **5b**, m.p. 112° ; **c**, 106°; **d**, 170°; **e**, 98°; **f**, 173° ; **g**, 148°; **h**, 177° ; **i**, 157°; **j**, 172°; **k**, 86°; **l**, 81°.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to D.S.T., New Delhi for financial support.

References

- V. K. AHLUWALIA, R. R. MANN and S. BALA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 608; V. K. AHLUWALIA, N. MALIKA and S. KUMARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 1021; N. K. SANGWAN, B. S. VERMA, O. P. MALIK, and K. S. DHINDSA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, **29**, 294.
- M. V. PARANJPE and K. N. WADODKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 808; V. N. DOLKIA and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 813; M. B. HOGALE (DESHMUKH) and D. R. KHARADE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 298; W. U. MALIK, V. K. MAHESH and M. RAISINGHANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **9**, 655.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th. ed., Longman, London, 1980, p. 1104.